

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D2.4

Interim SWOT Analysis of WP2 Product Implementation

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Executive Summary

This interim analysis of Work Package 2's (WP2) Product Implementation highlights strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) identified during the first two years of the project. These findings demonstrate that the tasks and deliverables for the period have been met, and even exceeded, while also illustrating a need for further strategizing, especially for products that require legacy plans beyond PREP4BLUE's term in order to avoid losing tools instrumental to the Mission.

Strengths:

- High Engagement & Reach: WP2's social media campaigns, particularly the "Generation Blue" campaign, achieved exceptional reach and engagement.
- Comprehensive Communication Strategy: Completion of the Narrative Guide (D2.1), Communication Strategy (D2.2), dynamic web-experience, Digital Academy, Digital Trello Board/PDF Toolkits, and Communications Collaborative enhanced communications.
- Collaborative Networking: Proactive participation in numerous events, meetings, etc., have bolstered the visibility of Mission initiatives and formed many successful relationships.
- The "Mission Ocean and Waters Web-Experience" is a useful resource for information related to the Mission as it fosters a sense of community and shared goals among users.

Weaknesses:

- Complex Processes: Navigating EU interventions, particularly in branding (where there is much confusion), media, and events, has required significant additional resources and time.
- Sustainability Concerns: The long-term sustainability of platforms created for the Mission remains uncertain due to the funding and time-limited nature of CSAs.
- Content Overlap and Redundancy: The establishment of the MIP (as a tender) and multiple web-based services and sites have resulted in confusion and redundancy, necessitating a strategic shift to focus on unique and engaging content rather than duplicate efforts.
- The web-experience faces substantial technical, practical, and operational challenges stemming from the use of new technologies and the complex Mission structures.

Opportunities:

- Expansion of Social Media Presence: There is significant potential to expand digital/paid campaigns, utilize platforms such as TikTok, and adapt new formats and multimedia storytelling to sustain audience engagement and enrich the Mission's narrative.
- Increased Collaboration: Strengthening the relationships with various communications teams, including the MIP and EC, can potentially streamline processes and improve the coherence of the Mission's branding and messaging as well as help with legacy plans.
- The Web Experience could be substantially useful as a public face of the Mission, offering highlights of Mission contributions and by being complementary to other online sources.

Threats:

- Regulatory and Compliance Issues: The complexity of rules governing engagement between the EC, MIP, CSAs, and other projects could lead to challenges, especially in media.
- Potential Loss of Digital Assets: Without a sustainability plan, the digital assets and online presence built during the project may be at risk once funding ends.
- The web-experience will need to be updated regularly, carefully address multilingualism, and master the technologies employed to be successful.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
P4B	PREP4BLUE
SWOT	strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats
the Mission	Mission Ocean and Waters
DX.X	Deliverable (by number)
WP2	Work Package 2 (within PREP4BLUE)
MIP	Mission Implementation Platform
EC	European Commission
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
KDM	Konsortium Deutsche Meeresforschung
O	Objective (by number as noted in the grant agreement)

1 Introduction

Work Package 2 (WP2 – Creating a Visionary Narrative, Communications & Spaces) is led by KDM and focuses on communicating the Mission. Through the creation of various print, digital, and web-based tools, WP2 aims to build on and connect the many existing projects and initiatives at the EU, national, and local levels, as well as inspire awe and wonder around the ocean - connecting people with things they deeply value and welcome – and eliciting interest in taking action.

WP2's original objectives, tasks, and deliverables from the grant agreement are noted below. However, as is the case often with CSAs who are unaware of activities happening prior to funding and by other institutions, such as the EC, WP2's objectives, tasks, and deliverables were adjusted post-funding to meet the new demands and situational aspects and expectations of the project. For example, while we noted we would create the branding, the EC had already done that prior to our funding so our focus shifted to promoting the branding. Additionally, to avoid confusion with other websites and duplicating other content, we rebranded missionoceanwaters.eu so that people have a much more engaging “web-experience”. Refer to D2.3 *“Report on virtual space pilot and website including overview of existing Mission contributions and spaces for Mission-related events”* for more information on adjustments made to WP2's work post-funding and after multiple discussions with the EC, MIP, and other partners.

The original objectives (O), tasks, and deliverables as noted in the grant agreement include:

- **O1:** Develop a strong Mission Narrative as a means of realising a transformative and systemic portfolio approach to support the Mission and its activities
- **O2:** Prepare an overarching Mission Communication Strategy by providing key messaging and visionary visual examples based on the best available science and innovation, tailor-made for various audiences, and including social, digital, and traditional media
- **O3:** Support preparation of the Mission Implementation Platform and its Forum by designing and piloting innovative physical and virtual Mission Spaces for the Mission community and general population

WP2's tasks include:

- **Task 2.1 – Develop Mission Narrative Guide (Duration: M1-M6):** Based on the work of the Mission Board and legal texts, the aim is to produce a Mission Narrative Guide (D2.1) to help (i) Mission contributors understand the larger effort they are part of and (ii) make the Mission's relevance intuitively clear to European citizens, regardless of age, education, gender, ethnicity or background. WP2 will host at least two workshops/interactive events (in different LH Basins) specifically targeting the Mission contributors (internal), but with activities open to all interested parties - the first one ideally taking place early in the project in conjunction with a visible event (*e.g.*, during the French EU Council Presidency). Moderated by professional media and social science experts, and including designers, artists, activists, etc., the workshops will support the development of guidelines with the main Mission slogan/motto, key messaging regarding what the Mission actually is, and key concepts, definitions, and ideas (in line with official Mission documents). We will draw on perception surveys (*e.g.*, on emotional disconnect) and work with other initiatives, notably the European Bauhaus, to ensure a unified narrative. We will implement a testing phase using other WPs and citizen engagement (T3.4) confirming assess effectiveness of messages for different

audiences. Results will be used to fine-tune the Narrative Guide elements for use in the overarching Mission Communication Strategy.

- **Task 2.2 – Develop Overarching Communication Strategy** (Duration: M1-M9): Working with the EC, and the Mission implementation platform, T2.2 will prepare the overarching Mission Communication Strategy (D2.2), including branding elements such as the corporate design for the mission, Narrative Guide elements, and incorporating social/digital media. The work will be structured in the following steps: scoping, research (e.g., mapping perceptions and types of mission contributions), analysis, and pilot test. A branding guidebook with multimedia elements will be produced; subsequent deliverables could include subchapters for replicability to use across future networks. It will propose inspirational and emblematic science and innovation-based images and messages to aid Mission communication goals, including visualizing the narrative (T2.1).
- **Task 2.3 – Narrative & Strategy Testing Through Pilot Campaigns & Spaces** (Duration: M1-M36): T2.3 will pilot the narrative and Communications Strategy through a social media campaign, virtual spaces, and intergenerational and inclusive physical spaces as venues for meetings, interactions, exhibitions, etc., to engage Mission contributors and citizens across Europe. The task will organise at least two exhibitions/public events in iconic spaces (e.g., Ocean Space | Venice) with artists, designers, architects, the European Bauhaus, and other initiatives to showcase the Mission and its contributors. These products will be positioned as globally-visible contributions to the UN Ocean Decade.
 - *Subtask 2.3.1: Pilot a social media campaign, including public competitions, aimed at bringing Mission information to young people.* The Terms of Reference will be part of the Communication Strategy. This task will draw on and coordinate with T3.4 and other campaigns across Europe to engage citizens.
 - *Subtask 2.3.2: Conceptualize, design, and pilot an interactive, multidimensional virtual Mission space (website), including an overview of all Mission contributions and Mission-related events.* During the coronavirus pandemic, online venue technology has increased dramatically. This task will include working with online venue developers to explore the most advanced, open-source, accessible (CMS) software available and develop a virtual space pilot. This space will include a lobby, information booth, several auditoriums, cinema, exhibition hall, social media wall, etc., and ideally serve as a model, or the actual website, for the duration of the Mission. Working with WP4 WP6 and others, this task will showcase progress in Mission implementation (e.g., a Progress Dashboard and Map), including, where possible, increased restoration efforts and their impact on communities. It is intended be used by both the public and mission community with public and private (log-in) spaces featuring tools and information to aid both. We will work with other EU Missions (e.g., cities), living labs, citizen initiatives, etc. in order ensure inclusivity.
 - *Subtask 2.3.3: Conceptualise, design, and pilot with potential venues (e.g., museums and aquaria) from around the world physical Mission spaces that serve to exhibit Mission contributions and as venues to hold Mission-related activities (e.g., citizen assemblies, foresight workshops, future labs, etc.) in Europe.* The budget for implementing this subtask will be allocated when the Terms of Reference have been finalized. A close cooperation/co-location with WP3 is foreseen.

A report on accomplishments (D2.3) was produced and submitted previously, and this SWOT analysis at mid-term (D2.4) will help us to make adjustments before a final analysis and recommendations (D2.5) are produced at the end of the project in 2025.

2 Methods

With the assistance of a contractor (Joanne Sweeney of the Digital Training Institute), WP2 compiled statistics from social media channels, the Digital Academy, Trello Board, and the web-experience (missionoceanwaters.eu). WP2 also compiled a list of all activities completed to date in support of communication of the Mission and referred to other documents for assessment of our activities.

Refer to the Annex for the Generation Blue Campaign and YTD Social Media Reports, and see the table below (Table 2) in the Results section for a complete list of tasks completed and items/services produced. The Results section below also contains subsections with our SWOT analysis and some General Blue social media campaign statistics (Figures 1 and 2).

3 Results

In the first two of three years of the project, WP2 has completed all tasks and deliverables except for the final event noted in Subtask 2.3.3 and the final report, D2.5, both of which will be completed in 2025. Additionally, WP2 created and implemented a number of other helpful tools and resources as well as attended multiple events that resulted in several mini-campaigns on social media. Collectively, these activities served to aid and promote the Mission and key players in the community.

Table 2. Tasks, Deliverables & Other Products & Services WP2 Developed & Implemented from mid-2022 to mid-2024.

WP2 Product	Link
<p><i>Mission Ocean & Waters Narrative Guide (D2.1):</i> This guide was developed to facilitate storytelling about the Mission, fostering a sense of connection and empathy among the public.</p>	<p>The Narrative Guide is available on the Trello Board for all partners, elements of the Narrative Guide are incorporated into the web-experience at missionoceanwaters.eu, and the guide is also referenced in the Communication Strategy, which was shared with all partners via the public Trello Board. Narrative Guide: https://trello.com/c/UrcREakR and doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944248</p>
<p><i>Mission Ocean & Waters Communication Strategy (D2.2):</i> A cohesive communication strategy was devised to ensure consistent branding and enhance public recognition of the Mission.</p>	<p>Communication Strategy: https://trello.com/c/qcAyfDss and doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944488</p>
<p><i>Communications Collaborative Working Group (Other):</i> This platform facilitates collaboration among Mission communication partners as described above. While started by WP2, the group was eventually handed over to the MIP to avoid duplicative efforts.</p>	<p>NA – to request to join the Communications Collaborative, partners are instructed to email the MIP at MIP-editorialboard@technopolis-group.com</p>

<p><u>Missionoceanwaters.eu</u> web-experience (Subtask 2.3.2): Designed to complement the EC’s website, this web-experience features testimonials, interviews, and visually compelling content to capture the public’s attention and engagement by showcasing Mission Lighthouses and individual contributions through immersive scenes.</p>	<p>https://missionoceanwaters.eu</p>
<p>Social media channels (Task 2.2) & several campaigns (Subtask 2.3.1) : Seven social media channels are utilised to disseminate calls to action, event updates, videos, photos, and relevant information tailored to the target audience, including specialised campaigns. Several social media campaigns were held, including Lighthouse and other events to promote the Mission (often at the EC’s request) as well as our own “Generation Blue” campaign featuring original content from 4 mobile journalists (MoJos) to engage youth and change up the narrative for enhanced citizen engagement. Collectively, WP2 travelled to more than 10 events across Europe to publicize the Mission live on social media.</p>	<p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/missionoceaneu Twitter: https://twitter.com/ourmissionocean LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/missionocean/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/missionoceaneu/ TikTok: https://www.tiktok.com/missionoceanwaters Pinterest: http://pinterest.com/missionoceanwaters/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC8Zj1TyDAUuDO8QNLnd9zw</p>
<p>Trello Board (Other): A comprehensive Trello Board (Trello.com - an online tool for sharing resources) serves as a centralised repository of public information, tools, resources, and links related to the Mission, facilitating accessibility and dissemination of information.</p>	<p>https://bit.ly/MissionOceanSocialMedia</p>
<p>PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit (Other): This toolkit, available in PDF format, serves as a resource for new projects, equipping them with the necessary materials to promote the Mission effectively. It’s in the process of being updated and the revised version will be published in May 2024. This document was produced at the EC’s request to complement the Trello Board.</p>	<p>https://trello.com/c/Adz09TaT</p>
<p>Mission Ocean & Waters Digital Academy (Other): An exclusive platform for project partners and charter signatories was established to provide training on utilizing social media and other communication tools to promote the Mission and their respective roles within it. It’s been advertised as a bonus for Charter signatories.</p>	<p>https://psmi.kartra.com/portal/missionocean</p>
<p>V.ECOP Days 2024 (Subtask 2.3.3): The Virtual Early Career Ocean Professional (V.ECOP) Days were a unique livestream event series showcasing testimonies of change in applying science and knowledge to ocean sustainability from the global community of ECOPs. Hosted by and for ECOPs as a contribution to the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, on-site ECOP mobile journalists provided live coverage to showcase commitments to both the Decade and the Mission.</p>	<p>https://Vecop.net</p>

Using the information contained in the reports; personal analysis of the work involved and completed; and evaluation of experiences at events, in meetings, and through various correspondence, WP2 posits the following with respect to the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with its communications work on behalf of the Mission.

3.1 Strengths

- **Achievement of Original Goals:** Successfully completed all planned tasks and deliverables including the Narrative Guide (D2.1), Communication Strategy (D2.2), web-experience (Subtask 2.3.2), social media campaign (Subtask 2.3.1), innovative event (Subtask 2.3.3), social media channels (Task 2.2), etc.
- **Exceeded Expectations with Additional Tools, Products, and Services :** Delivered additional helpful outputs such as several mini social media campaigns, two comprehensive Communication Toolkits (one digital via the Trello Board and one in PDF form), a Digital Academy for those who endorsed the Charter, attended several more events than anticipated, and promoted hundreds of events and projects on social media – all beyond the initial scope of the grant agreement.
- **Collaborative Networking:** Established a robust Communications Collaborative Working Group and regularly conducted monthly meetings involving diverse stakeholders, enhancing collaboration and information sharing. The synergy created through the working group boosted the outreach and impact of the Mission’s messages, fostering a unified voice and approach and leading to improved communication effectiveness across the board. The group meets monthly and approximately 50 people attend.
- **Visible and Robust Attendance & Engagement:** WP2 has been proactive in participating in numerous events, significantly enhancing the visibility and engagement of Mission Ocean & Waters initiatives. Such networking through regular meetings and events contributed also to the visibility and engagement of the Mission initiatives. This participation was well beyond the initial scope and instrumental in growing the Mission Ocean & Waters audience and engagement. The team's involvement in various EC-requested events demonstrated their commitment and adaptability.
- **Effective Social Media Campaigns:** The social media campaigns achieved high engagement and reach with significant growth in followers and impressions across platforms. For instance, the Generation Blue campaign achieved 2.84 million impressions and high engagement across Facebook and Instagram. This approach increased engagement through fresher and more relatable content and brought additional narratives to the audience.
 - Breakdown of Generation Blue campaign (Figure 1 & Figure 2 & full campaign report in Annex)
 - 732 social media posts published across all platforms over two weeks;
 - Cumulative reach of 31.2K from TikTok, Facebook, and Instagram;
 - 2.84 million total impressions from LinkedIn, Instagram, and Facebook;
 - 2 million hashtag impacts/impressions from #GenerationBlue and #MissionOcean.
- **Web-Experience:**
 - Engagement and Interaction: The web-experience features interactive pages designed to enhance user engagement by showcasing Mission Lighthouses and individual contributions through immersive scenes.

- Community Building: The narrative structure of the web-experience, organized around "My Mission, Our Mission, and EU Mission," effectively fosters a sense of community and shared goals among users.
- Comprehensive Content: The web-experience includes numerous testimonials, contributions from various EU projects, and references many initiatives, making it a useful resource for information related to the Mission.

3.1.1 Campaign Statistics

Figure 1. From April 1-14 during the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels, more than 400,000 impressions were made from the #GenerationBlue hashtag. (Source/Credit: KDM & Digital Training Institute on behalf of PREP4BLUE)

Figure 2. From April 1-14 during the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels, more than 1,600,000 impressions were made from the #MissionOcean hashtag. (Source/Credit : KDM & Digital Training)

3.2 Weaknesses

- **Sustainability & Legacy Concerns:** There are potential sustainability issues for the digital platforms (web-experience, social media channels, Digital Academy, Trello Board, etc.) given the time and funding-limited nature of CSAs as well as the EC's rules on social media channels and the related complications in establishing a long-term plan for such platforms. The sustainability of the digital platforms created for the Mission therefore remains uncertain beyond the CSA funding period. The intricacies of working out a long-term plan raise concerns about maintaining and possibly even losing these assets as well as continuing the engagement efforts once the initial funding ceases.
- **Complex EC Rules, Processes, and Expectations:** Challenges in navigating and complying with the European Commission's complex, and even contradictory, rules for branding and communications sometimes hampered effective collaboration, especially with partners who sought answers to their questions specifically on branding and communications but received mixes or even negative responses. Responses from the EC sometimes caused delays and confusion, hindering smooth operations. Additionally, the EC often misinterpreted our role as a CSA rather than a tender and often made requests that were well beyond the scope of our work and that of partners, for example, requesting that we attend so many events to cover on social media, or to create a PDF of the Trello Board to serve as a toolkit (neither were part of tasks/deliverables). These complexities, additional requests, etc. required additional time and resources on our part, impacting overall efficiency and morale.
- **Overlapping Tasks/Content & Redundancy:** Multiple web-based services and sites led to confusion and potential for redundancy, requiring a shift in focus while partners made an effort to discern who was responsible for doing what and how. For example, this led WP2 to emphasize more engaging and unique content on our web-experience, missionoceanwaters.eu. Additionally, the overlap between WP2 tasks and the MIP's tasks necessitated continuous coordination to avoid redundancy and ensure efficient resource use. For example, the MIP was officially tasked with creating a communications group, which we had already done. Rather than having two, the MIP assumed management of ours, the "Communications Collaborative".
- **Web-Experience:**
 - *Technical Challenges:* The web-experience development faced significant delays due to the need for filming in conjunction with Mission events and reprogramming to improve navigation. Adjustments to the web-experience are costly and time-consuming as they require programming work.
 - *User Experience Issues:* Feedback indicated difficulties with navigation, loading times, and browser compatibility, with many users encountering problems on Safari, Chrome, and Firefox.
 - *Content Gaps:* Initial feedback pointed out missing content and spelling errors that needed quick correction as the web-experience went live.

3.3 Opportunities

- **Expansion of Social Media Presence:** Continued growth and engagement on social media platforms can further enhance the project's visibility and impact.
 - *Leverage campaigns:* There is potential to expand digital campaigns leveraging the strong engagement metrics and broad reach achieved. Plans for future campaigns, including a paid campaign in collaboration with MIP/EC, can further amplify impact.
 - *Target specific audiences:* Further engaging youth and communities through targeted, but not necessarily paid, campaigns and storytelling can foster greater public interest and involvement.
- **Leveraging Networks:** The established collaborative networks can be leveraged to support more comprehensive and integrated communication strategies, increasing the project's reach and influence.
- **Innovative Content Formats:** Opportunity to explore new content formats and multimedia storytelling can keep the audience engaged. Continuing to document and share unique, impactful stories from contributors can enhance the Mission's narrative and content library.
- **Increased Collaboration with EC:** Strengthening the working relationship with the EC's communications teams and project officers could help streamline processes and enhance the coherence of the Mission's branding and messaging. This collaboration can lead to more efficient use of resources and better alignment with broader EU objectives.
- **Web-Experience:**
 - *Public Visibility:* There is an opportunity to make the web-experience the public face of the Mission, offering highlights of the contributions towards the Mission.
 - *Complementarity and Added Value:* By ensuring the web-experience complements existing Mission services (like the European Commission website and various Mission project websites), the web-experience can enhance its value and visibility.

3.4 Threats

- **Long-term Sustainability/Loss of Assets:** Without a long-term sustainability plan for the digital platforms, there is a risk that these valuable resources may be lost post-project. Ensuring the continuity of these platforms is crucial. Without a sustainable plan, there is a risk of losing the digital assets and the robust online presence built during the project once funding ends. Ensuring the continuity of these platforms is crucial.
- **Coordination Challenges:** The need for continuous coordination to manage overlapping tasks and ensure alignment with the EC, MIP, and numerous other partners could strain resources and operational efficiency.
- **Regulatory and Compliance Issues:** The complexity of rules governing engagement between the EC and CSAs can lead to overstep and compliance challenges, potentially disrupting ongoing efforts and causing delays. Such bureaucratic complexities may hinder the project's ability to maximize its impact or even continue on its current trajectory of increasing engagement.
- **Web-Experience:**
 - *Sustainability of Updates:* The ongoing need for programming work to make adjustments could strain resources and delay future updates, affecting the web-experience's long-term sustainability and relevance.

- *Multilingualism Challenges:* The complexity of providing content in multiple languages, especially when speakers prefer or insist on English, poses a significant challenge to effective communication and engagement.
- *Technological Dependencies:* Dependence on specific technologies and service providers for web experience functionality and filming might introduce vulnerabilities and affect the web-experience's stability and performance.

4 Conclusion

This SWOT analysis demonstrates that WP2 has delivered on the commitments outlined in the grant agreement. It has successfully delivered in terms of meeting its tasks and deliverables despite facing challenges. WP2 has demonstrated strengths in engagement, strategic communication, and collaborative networking. WP2 has made strides in achieving its goals, particularly through impactful social media campaigns, consistent collaboration with multiple partners, the production of multiple tools and resources, and events targeting a ECOPs (a key audience)- surpassing initial expectations.

However, challenges related to complex EU processes and rules, sustainability and legacy, content/task overlap, and excessive requests involving staff time and costs must be addressed to ensure the long-term success and efficiency of the project's communication efforts by partners moving forward and especially once PREP4BLUE ends.

The opportunities identified provide a path forward for leveraging the strengths and addressing the weaknesses to ensure continued success and impact. Utilizing the established networks and continuing to engage with new and diverse stakeholders will be crucial moving forward, as will the EC helping to determine legacy allowances, in spite of bureaucratic processes, and exercising appropriate restraint with non-tender partners.

5 ANNEXES

5.1	<u>GENERATION BLUE SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN REPORT</u>	<u>16</u>
5.2	<u>YTD MISSION OCEAN SOCIAL MEDIA REPORT</u>	<u>23</u>

5.1 Generation Blue Social Media Campaign Report

Generation Blue

Social Media Campaign Report

**Prepared by Joanne Sweeney,
Digital Training Institute**

April 2024

Campaign Overview

'Generation Blue' was a signature social media campaign for Mission Ocean channels to create a bridge between the EU institutions and the broader marine science online community to citizens. In late 2023 a public callout for youth MoJos (mobile journalists) was launched with the intention of attracting early career ocean professionals to unearth and document stories from across the European Commission's Lighthouse areas.

With a successful round of interviews, selection and training four MoJos were retained and briefed on their assignments:

- Find stories and testimonies of people, communities or organisations that are quietly making an impact on the Mission Ocean vision.
- These will be previously undocumented stories but that deserve to be documented and shared online.
- All stories should be produced in multi-media format.
- We build out a cross-platform online campaign during UN Ocean Decade Week and conference in Barcelona in April 2024.

STRATEGIC WINS | ORGANIC SOCIAL (NON-PAID)

- 22 stories collected from all four MoJos
- 732 social media posts published across all platforms
- Cumulative reach of 31.2K from TikTok, Facebook and Instagram
- 2.84M total impressions from LinkedIn, Instagram and Facebook
- 2M total X hashtag impacts/impressions from #GenerationBlue and #MissionOcean

MEET OUR FOUR MOJOS

TARA

MARIAM

LUCA

FIONA

Generation Blue Stories

PREP4BLUE Funded by the European Union

Generation Blue
Young Ocean Professional Contributions from Around the World

EU MISSIONS (MISSIONS FOR OCEAN AND WATER) #EUMissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

PREP4BLUE Funded by the European Union

Generation Blue
Young Ocean Professional Contributions from Around the World

FIONA UNESCO

EU MISSIONS (MISSIONS FOR OCEAN AND WATER) #EUMissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

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Generation Blue
Young Ocean Professional Contributions from Around the World

LUCA

EU MISSIONS (MISSIONS FOR OCEAN AND WATER) #EUMissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

PREP4BLUE Funded by the European Union

Generation Blue
Young Ocean Professional Contributions from Around the World

TARA MARIAM LUCA FIONA

EU MISSIONS (MISSIONS FOR OCEAN AND WATER) #EUMissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

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Generation Blue

The Dutch water quality has been embarrassingly bad for the past decades. And in the end, it's going to be the young people of now that are going to bear the issues that we've created with this in the future.

- WILLEM GROOTOONK

EU MISSIONS (MISSIONS FOR OCEAN AND WATER) #EUMissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

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Young Ocean Professional Contributions from Around the World

MARIAM

EU MISSIONS (MISSIONS FOR OCEAN AND WATER) #EUMissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

PREP4BLUE Funded by the European Union

Generation Blue
Young Ocean Professional Contributions from Around the World

TARA

EU MISSIONS (MISSIONS FOR OCEAN AND WATER) #EUMissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

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Generation Blue

I think the queer community and those who fight against climate change both stand up and question the "normal" way of doing things. They urge us to think differently and more creatively about how we live together and treat one another.

- CARLO DE GAETANO

EU MISSIONS (MISSIONS FOR OCEAN AND WATER) #EUMissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

Social Media Performance Report

1 April 2024 - 14 April 2024

Below are the key performance metrics demonstrating the impact and growth of the 'Generation Blue' social media campaign over the two-week period.

SOCIAL IMPACT AND GROWTH

X

- Posts 180 +847.4%
- Followers 1.8K +2.6%
- Engagement 766 +117.6%
- Likes 457 +97%
- Reposts 124 +18.1%

FACEBOOK

- Posts 138 +626.3%
- Fans 272 +51.1%
- Engagement 70K +113.1%
- Impressions 2.8M +197.7%
- Reach 14K +136.6%
- Video Views 445K +253.3%

LINKEDIN

- Posts 134 +538.1%
- Followers 2.3K +9.1%
- Engagement 1.8K +54.4%
- Impressions 32K +60.9%

INSTAGRAM

- Posts 203 +1168.8%
- Followers 468 +13.3%
- Engagement 614 +332.4%
- Impressions 10K +424.2%
- Reach 7.2K +294.7%

TIKTOK

- Posts 55
- Followers 10 +66.7%
- Engagement 81
- Reach 10K

PINTEREST

- Posts 22

732
Total Posts
Published

Facebook
Platform with
Highest Engagement

73.2K
Total
Engagements

2.84M
Total
Impressions

4.8K
Total
Fans/Followers

#GenerationBlue X Hashtag Report

1 April 2024 - 14 April 2024

SUMMARY

116 Media Posts (images, videos, links)	
66 Reposts	
311 Likes	
123,525 Potential Reach	

CONTRIBUTOR RANKINGS

Most Popular Contributors

- @HorizonEU | 180,683 Followers
- @EUScienceInnov | 133,985 Followers
- @CORDIS_EU | 49,723 Followers
- @AYCLearnDigital | 31,524 Followers
- @deepseadawn | 22,987 Followers

Most Active Contributors

- @OurMissionOcean | 98 Posts
- @StirBig | 10 Posts
- @LucaArfini | 9 Posts
- @PREP4BLUE | 8 Posts
- @BD_Stew | 5 Posts

#MissionOcean X Hashtag Report

1 April 2024 - 14 April 2024

SUMMARY

181 Media Posts (images, videos, links)	
176 Reposts	
647 Likes	
712,517 Potential Reach	

CONTRIBUTOR RANKINGS

Most Popular Contributors

- [@UNOceanDecade](#) | 20,946 Followers
- [@JSTweetsDigital](#) | 16,109 Followers
- [@BD_Stew](#) | 13,059 Followers
- [@Plasticsimpact](#) | 11,140 Followers
- [@BzGEO](#) | 9,630 Followers

Most Active Contributors

- [@OurMissionOcean](#) | 129 Posts
- [@PREP4BLUE](#) | 13 Posts
- [@LucaArfini](#) | 9 Posts
- [@bluemissionmed](#) | 9 Posts
- [@Stephen4EU](#) | 7 Posts

5.2 YTD Mission Ocean Social Media Report

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Mission Ocean Social Media

Final Reports (1 February 2023 – 26 May 2024)

Authors: Djameela Daniels (Digital Training), Wendy Namisnik (KDM), Stefan Fritz (KDM)

Type of deliverable: Report

Work package Leader: WP2 – KDM

Version: 0.3

GA No. 101056957 - PREP4BLUE

Start date of the project: June 1st, 2022

www.Pre4Blue.eu

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DISCLAIMER

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VERSIONING AND CONTRIBUTION HISTORY

Version	Date	Authors (Institution)	Notes
0.1	31.05.2024	Djameela Daniels (Digital Training), Wendy Namisnik (KDM), Stefan Fritz (KDM)	zipped folder with final social media reports for each platform for the date range 1 Feb 2023 - 26 May 2024
0.2	31.05.2024	Cécile NYS (Ifremer)	Conversion to Word document
0.3	03.06.2024	Cécile NYS (Ifremer)	Layout

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1 Facebook Page Report : Missionoceanwaters

1.1 Period 1 – From 1st February 2023 to 31st January 2024

1.1.1 Audience insights

Audience insights: Measure your performance by analyzing your Facebook Page activity

Audience growth

Number of fans gained and lost for the selected period.

New Organic Fans	47
New Paid Fans	0
Fans Lost (Unlikes)	1
New Fans (Net)	46

The total audience is
73 fans
 representing a variation of **+563.6%**
 compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Brand awareness score

Number of mentions of your page and shares of your content for the selected period.

Mentions	97
Shares	58
Brand awareness	155

The brand awareness score is
155
 representing a variation of **+2114.3%**
 compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Engagement

Number of fans interactions (reactions, comments, shares, clicks and private messages) with your Facebook page for the selected period.

Reactions	486
Link clicks	65
Clicks	327
Comments	6
Private messages	16
Shares	37
Total Engagement	937

The total engagement is
937 interactions
representing a variation of **+2502.8%**
compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Impressions

Number of times your page's content has been viewed during the selected period. This includes paid, organic and viral impressions.

Paid impressions	0
Organic impressions	12K
Viral impressions	7.1K
Total impressions	19K

The total impressions are
19,061
representing a variation of **+901.1%**
compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Overview

Key performance metrics for the selected period.

ROI

Value generated by your page for the selected period.

The total generated value is

€166.3

representing a variation of **+2669.4%**
compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Users' activity

Average day and hour users interacted the most with the page's content. Based on inbox activities (comments, private messages and post).

Video views

Number of time your page's videos has been viewed during the selected period.

Organic views / Paid views 978 / 0
 Clicked / Autoplay 49 / 929

Total views of videos are
978
 representing a variation of **+5047.4%**
 compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

1.1.2 Content summary

Content summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published content on your Facebook Page

Best day and time to publish

Average day and hour fans are most likely to engage with published posts.

Best post type to publish

Type of post fans are most likely to engage with.

Overview

Lifetime metrics of content published during the selected period.

<p>Posts published</p> <p>294</p> <p>+950.0%</p>	<p>Posts reach</p> <p>9,032</p> <p>+770.1%</p>	<p>Engaged users</p> <p>734</p> <p>+1429.2%</p>
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Publishing

Number of posts published during the selected period -with breakdown by type.

Status	Links	Photos	0
Videos			47
Total posts published			204
			43
			294

The total number of posts published is **294** representing a variation of **+950.0%** compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on reach.

Post Content	Reach	Engaged Users	Clicks	Other clicks	Engagement rate per reach	Engagement rate per impression
 Jun. 6 2023 Chloe O'Malley from Aran Islands shares their...	671	146	15	106	21.8%	19.8%
 Feb. 16 2023 You can now register to attend tomorrow's #Miss...	497	19	4	2	3.8%	3.6%
 Jan. 30 2024 Save the date	469	39	5	10	8.3%	7.7%

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on reach.

Post Content	Reach	Engaged Users	Clicks	Other clicks	Engagement rate per reach	Engagement rate per impression
 Feb. 24 2023 A powerful wave of actions for our ocean, seas & w...	393	10	2	2	2.5%	2.3%
 Jul. 12 2023 From the tiniest plankton to the mightiest whales,...	322	13	1	6	4%	3.5%
 Apr. 28 2023 From the tiniest plankton to the mightiest whale...	225	14	2	4	6.2%	5.6%

1.1.3 Community management

Community management: Understand the amount of work invested in your team's community management actions.

Overview

Key metrics of community management actions during the selected period.

Replies sent

Number of replies to comments and messages sent during the selected period.
This includes replies sent from other platforms (including Facebook).

The total number of replies is
6
 representing a variation of No data
 compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

1.2 Period 2 – From 1st February 2024 to 26th May 2024

1.2.1 Audience insights

Audience insights: Measure your performance by analyzing your Facebook Page activity

Audience growth

Number of fans gained and lost for the selected period.

New Organic Fans	189
New Paid Fans	77
Fans Lost (Unlikes)	12
New Fans (Net)	254

The total audience is
432 fans
representing a variation of **+491.8%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Brand awareness score

Number of mentions of your page and shares of your content for the selected period.

Mentions	274
Shares	98
Brand awareness	372

The brand awareness score is
372
representing a variation of **+601.9%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: age, gender, location and language.

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: age, gender, location and language.

By country

By city

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: age, gender, location and language.

By language

Engagement

Number of fans interactions (reactions, comments, shares, clicks and private messages) with your Facebook page for the selected period.

Reactions	4.8K
Link clicks	150K
Clicks	103K
Comments	17
Private messages	357
Shares	97
Total Engagement	258K

The total engagement is
258,460 interactions
representing a variation of **+96701.5%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Impressions

Number of times your page's content has been viewed during the selected period.
This includes paid, organic and viral impressions.

Paid impressions	10M
Organic impressions	56K
Viral impressions	24K
Total impressions	10M

The total impressions are
10M
representing a variation of **+132431.6%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Overview

Key performance metrics for the selected period.

Fans 432 +491.8%	Engagement 258,460 +96701.5%	Impressions 10M +132431.6%	Brand awareness 372 +601.9%
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ROI

Value generated by your page for the selected period.

The total generated value is
€202,486.1
 representing a variation of **+355045.3%**
 compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Users' activity

Average day and hour users interacted the most with the page's content.
 Based on inbox activities (comments, private messages and post).

Video views

Number of time your page's videos has been viewed during the selected period.

Organic views / Paid views	5.2K / 1.4M
Clicked / Autoplay	16K / 1.4M

Total views of videos are
1,436,153
representing a variation of **+983566.4%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

1.2.2 Content summary

Content summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published content on your Facebook Page

Best day and time to publish

Average day and hour fans are most likely to engage with published posts.

Best post type to publish

Type of post fans are most likely to engage with.

Overview

Lifetime metrics of content published during the selected period.

Publishing

Number of posts published during the selected period -with breakdown by type.

Status	Links	Photos	0
Videos			19
Total published	posts		196
			81
			296

The total number of posts published is **296**

representing a variation of **+179.2%** compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on reach.

Apr. 6 2024

We're thrilled to introduce our esteemed hosts ...

Reach	1.8K
Engaged Users	92
Clicks	52
Other clicks	54
Engagement rate per reach	5%
Engagement rate per impression	4.7%

Mar. 22 2024

Ready to make waves of change?

Reach	1.6K
Engaged Users	41
Clicks	12
Other clicks	6
Engagement rate per reach	2.6%
Engagement rate per impression	2.4%

Apr. 8 2024

Listen closely as Aakriti, our host from Asia, sha...

Reach	975
Engaged Users	415
Clicks	0
Other clicks	391
Engagement rate per reach	42.6%
Engagement rate per impression	40.9%

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on reach.

<p>Feb. 21 2024</p> <p>APPLICATIONS NOW OPEN FOR #VECOP24</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>Reach</td><td>583</td></tr> <tr><td>Engaged Users</td><td>49</td></tr> <tr><td>Clicks</td><td>19</td></tr> <tr><td>Other clicks</td><td>13</td></tr> <tr><td>Engagement rate per reach</td><td>8.4%</td></tr> <tr><td>Engagement rate per impression</td><td>7.7%</td></tr> </table>	Reach	583	Engaged Users	49	Clicks	19	Other clicks	13	Engagement rate per reach	8.4%	Engagement rate per impression	7.7%																										
Reach	636																																					
Engaged Users	37																																					
Clicks	20																																					
Other clicks	16																																					
Engagement rate per reach	5.8%																																					
Engagement rate per impression	5.3%																																					
Reach	620																																					
Engaged Users	15																																					
Clicks	6																																					
Other clicks	3																																					
Engagement rate per reach	2.4%																																					
Engagement rate per impression	2.4%																																					
Reach	583																																					
Engaged Users	49																																					
Clicks	19																																					
Other clicks	13																																					
Engagement rate per reach	8.4%																																					
Engagement rate per impression	7.7%																																					

1.2.3 Community management

Community management: Understand the amount of work invested in your team's community management actions.

2 Instagram Profile Report : Mission Ocean

2.1 Period 1 – From 1st February 2023 to 31st January 2024

2.1.1 Audience insights

Audience insights: Measure your performance by analyzing your Instagram Page activity

Audience growth

Number of followers gained during the selected period.

Gained followers	277
Lost followers	14
Total added followers	263
Total followers	315

The total audience is

315

representing a variation of No data compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Brand awareness score

Number of mentions of your brand account and listening searches containing your brand name and links to your website.

Mentions	59
Story mentions	117
Total brand awareness	176

The brand awareness score is

176

representing a variation of No data compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: age, gender, location and language.

Your average follower is a
25-34 years old Female
from
Italy

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: age, gender, location and language.

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: age, gender, location and language.

By country

By city

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: age, gender, location and language.

By language

Engagement

Number of interactions (likes, saved, comments, shares and direct messages) with your profile for the selected period.

Likes	441
Saved	8
Comments	6
Shares	11
Direct messages	117
Total interactions	583
Engagement rate per impressions	2.1%

The total engagement is
583 interactions
representing a variation of No data
compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Hashtags & interactions

Number of interactions generated by hashtags used in your posts.

#missionocean 1217 Interactions	#horizoneu 1109 Interactions	#eumissions 985 Interactions	#eumission 145 Interactions
#marinescience 71 Interactions	#missionocean#eumissions#horizoneu 52 Interactions	#mission 48 Interactions	#oceans 45 Interactions
#euequalpayday 35 Interactions	#ocean 30 Interactions	#contentcreator 27 Interactions	#oceanliteracy 24 Interactions
#knowledge 22 Interactions	#seaweed 21 Interactions	#eu4ocean 21 Interactions	#horizoneu 21 Interactions
#oceanconservation 20 Interactions	#page0 20 Interactions	#innovation 19 Interactions	#research 19 Interactions

Impressions

Number of times your profile's content has been viewed during the selected period.

Organic impressions	27K
Paid impressions	0
Total impressions	27K

The total impressions are

27,234

representing a variation of No data compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Overview

Key performance metrics for the selected period.

Followers 315 No data	Engagement 583 No data	Impressions 27,234 No data	Brand awareness 176 No data
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Reach

Number of unique users who have viewed your profiles content during the selected period.

Paid reach	0
Organic reach	17K
Total reach	17K

The total reach is

17,321

representing a variation of No data compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

2.1.2 Content summary

Content summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published content on your Instagram Page

Best day and time to publish

Average day and hour followers are most likely to engage with published posts.

Best post type to publish

Type of post followers are most likely to engage with.

Overview

Lifetime metrics of content published during the selected period.

Posts published

331

No data

Posts reach

17,054

No data

Posts engagement

1,542

No data

Publishing

Number of posts published during the selected period -with breakdown by type.

Images	126
Videos	1
Carousel	2
Stories	157
Reels	45
Total posts published	331

The total number of posts published is
331
representing a variation of No data
compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on reach.

Jun. 4 2023
Meet Chloe Ní Mhaílle from the Aran Islands, off I...

Reach	1.4K
Comments	2
Likes	130
Saved	3
Engagement	137
Engagement rate per reach	9.8%
Engagement rate per impression	8.2%

Jun. 28 2023
Lily Xu Lijia is an 2012 Olympic Sailing Gold Meda...

Reach	434
Comments	0
Likes	7
Saved	0
Engagement	8
Engagement rate per reach	1.8%
Engagement rate per impression	1.8%

May. 30 2023
Meet Pepper!

Reach	412
Comments	2
Likes	18
Saved	2
Engagement	24
Engagement rate per reach	5.8%
Engagement rate per impression	4.9%

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on reach.

Post Image	Date	Caption	Reach	Comments	Likes	Saved	Engagement	Engagement rate per reach	Engagement rate per impression
	Apr. 26 2023	🌊 THE POWER & VALUE OF SEAWEED	403	0	12	1	15	3.7%	3.6%
	Aug. 3 2023	🌊 Join us in supporting the Mission Ocean charter...	402	0	13	0	14	3.5%	3.5%
	Jul. 12 2023	📱 We need YOU!	384	0	11	0	15	3.9%	3.4%

2.1.3 Stories summary

Stories summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published stories on your Instagram Profile

Overview

Key metrics of Stories published during the selected period.

<p>Stories published</p> <p>157</p> <p>No data</p>	<p>Stories reach</p> <p>5,402</p> <p>No data</p>	<p>Stories engagement</p> <p>3</p> <p>No data</p>	<p>Stories impressions</p> <p>5,368</p> <p>No data</p>
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Top content

Best performing Stories published during the selected period. Based on reach.

Top content

Best performing Stories published during the selected period. Based on reach.

2.1.4 Community management

Community management: Understand the amount of work invested in your team's community management actions.

Overview

Key metrics of community management actions during the selected period.

Replies sent

Number of replies to comments sent during the selected period.

The total number of replies is
11
 representing a variation of No data
 compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

2.2 Period 2 – From 1st February 2024 to 26th May 2024

2.2.1 Audience insights

Audience insights: Measure your performance by analyzing your Instagram Page activity

Audience growth

Number of followers gained during the selected period.

Gained followers	213
Lost followers	30
Total added followers	183
Total followers	518

The total audience is

518

representing a variation of **+64.4%**
 compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Brand awareness score

Number of mentions of your brand account and listening searches containing your brand name and links to your website.

Mentions	12
Story mentions	1
Total brand awareness	15
	8
	27
	9

The brand awareness score is

279

representing a variation of **+350.0%**
 compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: age, gender, location and language.

Your average follower is a
25-34 years old Female
from
Italy

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: age, gender, location and language.

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: age, gender, location and language.

Engagement

Number of interactions (likes, saved, comments, shares and direct messages) with your profile for the selected period.

Likes	3.2K
Saved	130
Comments	36
Shares	213
Direct messages	79
Total interactions	3.6K
Engagement rate per impressions	14.7%

The total engagement is
3,615 interactions
representing a variation of **+645.4%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 – Jan. 31 2024

Hashtags & interactions

Number of interactions generated by hashtags used in your posts.

#missionocean 1170 Interactions	#horizoneu 710 Interactions	#eumissions 671 Interactions	#generationblue 613 Interactions
#ecops 327 Interactions	#vecops24 283 Interactions	#marine 83 Interactions	#oceanecodec 60 Interactions
#communities 49 Interactions	#opencall 44 Interactions	#litter 36 Interactions	#euoceanecodec 35 Interactions
#ecopdays24 33 Interactions	#vecop24 33 Interactions	#innovations 33 Interactions	#sustainable 33 Interactions
#activists 32 Interactions	#experts 32 Interactions	#plastics 32 Interactions	#reduce 32 Interactions

Impressions

Number of times your profile's content has been viewed during the selected period.

Organic impressions	25K
Paid impressions	0
Total impressions	25K

The total impressions are

24,601

representing a variation of **+208.2%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Overview

Key performance metrics for the selected period.

Followers 518 +64.4%	Engagement 3,615 +645.4%	Impressions 24,601 +208.2%	Brand awareness 279 +350.0%
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Reach

Number of unique users who have viewed your profiles content during the selected period.

Paid reach	0
Organic reach	11K
Total reach	11K

The total reach is
11,027
 representing a variation of **+123.5%**
 compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Users' activity

Average number of your followers online on Instagram by hours and day over the selected period.

2.2.2 Content summary

Content summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published content on your Instagram Page

Best day and time to publish

Average day and hour followers are most likely to engage with published posts.

Best post type to publish

Type of post followers are most likely to engage with.

Overview

Lifetime metrics of content published during the selected period.

Publishing

Number of posts published during the selected period -with breakdown by type.

Images	140
Videos	0
Carousel	9
Stories	110
Reels	76
Total posts published	335

The total number of posts published is
335
representing a variation of **+264.1%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on reach.

Mar. 22 2024

[Dive into change!](#)

Reach	476
Comments	0
Likes	12
Saved	2
Engagement	20
Engagement rate per reach	4.2%
Engagement rate per impression	3.6%

Apr. 12 2024

In this enlightening clip from @mariamavakova 's i...

Reach	438
Comments	0
Likes	4
Saved	1
Engagement	6
Engagement rate per reach	1.4%
Engagement rate per impression	1.4%

Mar. 5 2024

Mission Ocean project @restore4life.eu coor...

Reach	380
Comments	1
Likes	21
Saved	0
Engagement	25
Engagement rate per reach	6.6%
Engagement rate per impression	5.6%

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on reach.

Thumbnail	Date	Title	Reach	Comments	Likes	Saved	Engagement	Engagement rate per reach	Engagement rate per impression
	Apr. 7 2024	A heartfelt journey of change with Fiona, our este...	356	5	18	0	24	6.7%	6.3%
	Mar. 5 2024	Sahar Stevenson-Jones explains how Mission Ocea...	263	1	12	0	14	5.3%	4.6%
	Mar. 6 2024	The team from BlueMissionMed take us through ho...	246	3	29	1	35	14.2%	11.1%

2.2.3 Stories summary

Stories summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published stories on your Instagram Profile

Overview

Key metrics of Stories published during the selected period.

<p>Stories impressions</p> <p>1,401</p> <p>+4.5%</p>			
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Top content

Best performing Stories published during the selected period. Based on reach.

Top content

Best performing Stories published during the selected period. Based on reach.

2.2.4 Community management

Community management: Understand the amount of work invested in your team's community management actions.

Overview

Key metrics of community management actions during the selected period.

Replies sent

Number of replies to comments sent during the selected period.

The total number of replies is
1
 representing a variation of +0.0%
 compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

3 LinkedIn Page Report : Mission Ocean

3.1 Period 1 – From 1st February 2023 to 31st January 2024

3.1.1 Audience insights

Audience insights: Measure your performance by analysing your LinkedIn Page activity

Audience growth

Number of net followers gained during the selected period.

New organic followers	1.2K
New paid followers	0
Total new followers	1.2K

The total audience is
1,188 followers
 representing a variation of No data
 compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: country, seniority, company size and position.

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: country, seniority, company size and position.

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: country, seniority, company size and position.

Engagement

Number of followers interactions (likes, comments, clicks and shares) with your LinkedIn page for the selected period.

Likes	3.4K
Comments	47
Clicks	2.4K
Shares	325
Total interactions	6.2K
Engagement rate per impressions	8.1%

The total engagement is **6,171 interactions** representing a variation of No data compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Impressions

Number of times your page's content has been viewed during the selected period.

The total reached users are **36,172** representing a variation of No data compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

The total impressions are **76,584** representing a variation of No data compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Overview

Key performance metrics for the selected period.

Users' activity

Average day and hour users interacted the most with the profile's content.
Based on inbox activities (comments).

3.1.2 Content summary

Content summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published content on your LinkedIn Page

Best day and time to publish

Average day and hour followers are most likely to engage with published posts.

Overview

Lifetime metrics of content published during the selected period.

<p>Posts published</p> <p>291</p> <p>No data</p>	<p>Posts impressions</p> <p>75,884</p> <p>No data</p>	<p>Posts engagement</p> <p>6,289</p> <p>No data</p>
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Publishing

Number of posts published during the selected period .

The total number of posts published is
291
 representing a variation of No data
 compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on impressions.

Oct. 16 2023
! Open Call: Boosting the deployment of plastic lit...

Impressions	1.1K
Clicks	31
Likes	23
Shares	10
Comments	0
Engagement	64
Engagement rate per reach	8%
Engagement rate per impression	5.8%

Jan. 2 2024
JUST ANNOUNCED

Impressions	988
Clicks	97
Likes	27
Shares	2
Comments	1
Engagement	127
Engagement rate per reach	31.8%
Engagement rate per impression	12.9%

Dec. 6 2023
Introducing the Blue Bio Match Platform: The Blue ...

Impressions	905
Clicks	28
Likes	45
Shares	11
Comments	1
Engagement	85
Engagement rate per reach	13.1%
Engagement rate per impression	14.3%

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on impressions.

Post Title	Date	Impressions	Clicks	Likes	Shares	Comments	Engagement	Engagement rate per reach	Engagement rate per impression
Save the date	Jan. 30 2024	904	35	65	7	0	107	19.6%	12.3%
We are proud to introduce CLIMAREST, an EU-funded ...	Dec. 12 2023	876	33	35	3	2	73	10.7%	8.3%
EU-funded projects work to protect #marine ecosyst...	Jan. 2 2024	839	15	17	2	0	34	8.3%	4.1%

3.2 Period 2 – From 1st February 2024 to 26th May 2024

3.2.1 Audience insights

Audience insights: Measure your performance by analyzing your LinkedIn Page activity

Audience growth

Number of net followers gained during the selected period.

New organic followers	1.4K
New paid followers	0
Total new followers	1.4K

The total audience is
2,584 followers
representing a variation of **+117.5%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: country, seniority, company size and position.

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: country, seniority, company size and position.

By country

By seniority

Demographics

Demographic information about your audience: country, seniority, company size and position.

Engagement

Number of followers interactions (likes, comments, clicks and shares) with your LinkedIn page for the selected period.

Likes	4.3K
Comments	59
Clicks	5K
Shares	175
Total interactions	9.6K
Engagement rate per impressions	6.6%

The total engagement is
9,578 interactions
representing a variation of **+231.2%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Impressions

Number of times your page's content has been viewed during the selected period.

The total reached users are

62,991

representing a variation of **+225.7%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

The total impressions are

144,663

representing a variation of **+270.7%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Overview

Key performance metrics for the selected period.

<p> Followers</p> <p>2,584</p> <p>+117.5%</p>	<p> Engagement</p> <p>9,578</p> <p>+231.2%</p>	<p> Impressions</p> <p>144,663</p> <p>+270.7%</p>
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Users' activity

Average day and hour users interacted the most with the profile's content.
Based on inbox activities (comments).

3.2.2 Content summary

Content summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published content on your LinkedIn Page

Best day and time to publish

Average day and hour followers are most likely to engage with published posts.

Overview

Lifetime metrics of content published during the selected period.

Publishing

Number of posts published during the selected period .

The total number of posts published is
298
 representing a variation of **+178.5%**
 compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on impressions.

Mar. 4 2024
Today marked an important moment for Mission Ocean...

Impressions	4.1K
Clicks	463
Likes	149
Shares	14
Comments	1
Engagement	627
Engagement rate per reach	22.5%
Engagement rate per impression	15.5%

Mar. 6 2024
Today at the European Parliament MEPs met with sig...

Impressions	3.9K
Clicks	148
Likes	153
Shares	20
Comments	0
Engagement	321
Engagement rate per reach	11.6%
Engagement rate per impression	8.2%

Mar. 22 2024
Ready to make waves of change?

Impressions	3.9K
Clicks	138
Likes	104
Shares	41
Comments	3
Engagement	286
Engagement rate per reach	10.9%
Engagement rate per impression	7.4%

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on impressions.

Mar. 5 2024
At the heart of the #MissionOcean and Waters drive...

Impressions	3.6K
Clicks	204
Likes	142
Shares	21
Comments	1
Engagement	368
Engagement rate per reach	14.5%
Engagement rate per impression	10.2%

Mar. 9 2024
A new EU guide to financing opportunities for the ...

Impressions	2.9K
Clicks	157
Likes	65
Shares	5
Comments	2
Engagement	229
Engagement rate per reach	11.5%
Engagement rate per impression	8%

Apr. 28 2024
Introducing Mission Ocean & Waters' lighthouses...

Impressions	1.8K
Clicks	49
Likes	88
Shares	11
Comments	2
Engagement	150
Engagement rate per reach	11.7%
Engagement rate per impression	8.4%

4 Pinterest

5 Tiktok Page Report : missionoceanwaters

5.1 Period 1 – From 1st February 2023 to 31st January 2024

5.1.1 Audience insights

Audience insights: Measure your performance by analyzing your Tiktok Page activity

Overview

Key performance metrics of your Tiktok page for the selected period.

Audience growth

Number of net followers gained during the selected period.

New Followers: 0
Total followers: 6

The total audience is

6

representing a variation of No data compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

5.1.2 Content summary

Content summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published content on your Tiktok Page

Best day and time to publish

Average day and hour when your audience watched the largest share of your videos (time spent watching your videos over total video duration).

Overview

Lifetime metrics of content published during the selected period.

Publishing

Number of posts published during the selected period -with breakdown by type.

The total number of posts published is
13
representing a variation of No data
compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on video completion rate.

Thumbnail	Date	Title	Reach	Video completion rate	Video replays	Watched fully	Impressions	Engagement	Engagement rate per reach	Engagement rate per impression
	Jun. 30 2023	Have you heard about the Mission Ocean charter?...	0	100.0%	0	0	0	0	0%	0%
	Jul. 5 2023	Our oceans are a vital part of our planet and t...	0	0.0%	189	0	189	1	0%	0.5%
	Jul. 12 2023	From the tiniest plankton to the mightiest whales,...	0	0.0%	13	0	<	<	0%	7.7%

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on video completion rate.

Thumbnail	Date	Title	Reach	Video completion rate	Video replays	Watched fully	Impressions	Engagement	Engagement rate per reach	Engagement rate per impression
	Jul. 19 2023	Did you know that our oceans play a vital role in ...	0	0.0%	3	0	3	0	0%	0%
	Jul. 27 2023	Do you want to join our social media team? F...	0	0.0%	204	0	204	0	0%	0%
	Jul. 27 2023	The Mission Ocean charter is a global effort to ...	0	0.0%	190	0	<	<	0%	1.1%

5.2 Period 2 – From 1st February 2024 to 26th May 2024

5.2.1 Audience insights

Audience insights: Measure your performance by analyzing your Tiktok Page activity

Audience growth

Number of net followers gained during the selected period.

New Followers 0
Total followers 13

The total audience is

13

representing a variation of **+116.7%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Overview

Key performance metrics of your Tiktok page for the selected period.

5.2.2 Content summary

Content summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published content on your Tiktok Page

Best day and time to publish

Average day and hour when your audience watched the largest share of your videos (time spent watching your videos over total video duration).

Overview

Lifetime metrics of content published during the selected period.

Publishing

Number of posts published during the selected period -with breakdown by type.

The total number of posts published is
48
 representing a variation of **+4700.0%**
 compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on video completion rate.

Video Title	Reach	Video completion rate	Video replays	Watched fully	Impressions	Engagement	Engagement rate per reach	Engagement rate per impression
Apr. 8 2024 Take a closer look at the melting glacier in the A...	245	45.7%	12	19	257	2	0.8%	0.8%
Apr. 7 2024 Witness the industrious spirit of a beaver as it n...	240	23.9%	13	9	253	1	0.4%	0.4%
Apr. 9 2024 As the V.ECOP Days happen, meet Denzel, our host f...	227	20.4%	31	9	<	<	0.4%	0.4%

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on video completion rate.

Thumbnail	Video Title	Date	Reach	Video completion rate	Video replays	Watched fully	Impressions	Engagement	Engagement rate per reach	Engagement rate per impression
	The SHORE consortium's first #OpenCall is still op...	Feb. 20 2024	814	18.4%	73	10	887	0	0%	0%
	Susana, our mobile journalist who will lead the VE...	Apr. 8 2024	234	18.1%	9	10	243	3	1.3%	1.2%
	In this insightful clip from Luca's interview with...	Apr. 11 2024	245	17.7%	24	4	<	<	0%	0%

6 X (Twitter) Profile report: Mission Ocean Waters

6.1 Period 1 – From 1st February 2023 to 31st January 2024

6.1.1 Audience insights

Audience insights: Measure your performance by analyzing your X (Twitter) Page activity

Audience growth

Number of net followers gained during the selected period.

New followers (net)	867
Total followers	1513

The total audience is
1513
representing a variation of **+186.0%**
compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Engagement

Number of followers' interactions (likes, replies and reposts) with your profile for the selected period.

Mentions	956
Likes	5.5K
Replies	81
Quote posts	44
Reposts	1.2K
Direct messages	37
Total interactions	7.8K

The total engagement is
7,764 interactions
representing a variation of **+520.6%**
compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Hashtags & interactions

Number of interactions generated by hashtags used in your posts.

#missionocean 8586 Interactions	#eumissions 4938 Interactions	#horizoneu 4575 Interactions	#contentcreators 353 Interactions
#oceans 341 Interactions	#atlanticall 339 Interactions	#missionarenabanos1 304 Interactions	#worldoceansday 291 Interactions
#oceanconservation 207 Interactions	#eumission 157 Interactions	#socialmedia 144 Interactions	#natura2000awards 136 Interactions
#prep4blue 135 Interactions	#emd2023 135 Interactions	#oceanawareness 125 Interactions	#ocean 118 Interactions
#oceancharter 115 Interactions	#galwaystatement10 113 Interactions	#mission 110 Interactions	#oceanwildlife 93 Interactions

Overview

Key performance metrics for the selected period.

Users' activity

Average day and hour users interacted the most with the profile's content. Based on inbox activities (mentions and direct messages).

6.1.2 Content summary

Content summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published content on your X (Twitter) Page

Best day and time to publish

Average day and hour followers are most likely to engage with published content.

Best post type to publish

Type of post followers are most likely to engage with.

Overview

Lifetime metrics of content published during the selected period.

Publishing

Number of Posts published during the selected period -with breakdown by type.

Text	35
Links	156
Photos/Videos	434
Total posts published	625

The total number of posts published is
625
representing a variation of **+468.2%**
compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on impressions.

This post had no picture linked.

Jul. 11 2023

We are hiring content creators

Impressions	5K
Likes	27
Reposts	18
Quote posts	9
Replies	2
Engagement	287
Engagement rate per impression	5.8%

Aug. 3 2023

Join us in supporting the Mission Ocean charter...

Impressions	4.5K
Likes	41
Reposts	24
Quote posts	1
Replies	2
Engagement	126
Engagement rate per impression	2.8%

The DIGITAL TWIN OCEAN

An interactive replica of the ocean for better decision-making

What is it?

A digital space providing access to vast amounts of data, models, artificial intelligence and other tools, which will allow the replication of the properties and behaviours of marine systems.

Jun. 20 2023

WHAT IS THE DIGITAL TWIN OCEAN?

Impressions	4.5K
Likes	50
Reposts	22
Quote posts	3
Replies	1
Engagement	154
Engagement rate per impression	4.4%

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on impressions.

Post Content	Impressions	Likes	Reposts	Quote posts	Replies	Engagement	Engagement rate per impression
 Jul. 31 2023 OPEN call for tenders #HorizonEU #EUMissions #O...	3.4K	36	26	0	1	119	3.5%
 Jun. 6 2023 Chloe O'Malley from Aran Islands shares their...	3.2K	29	7	2	0	171	5.4%
 Jun. 13 2023 Join us in supporting the Mission Ocean charter...	3.2K	25	9	1	0	58	2%

6.1.3 Community management

Community management: Understand the amount of work invested in your team's community management actions.

Overview

Key metrics of community management actions during the selected period.

AVG response time No data		
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Replies sent

Number of replies to comments sent during the selected period.

The total number of replies is

31

representing a variation of **+675.0%**
 compared to Feb. 1 2022 –Jan. 31 2023

6.2 Period 2 – From 1st February 2024 to 26th May 2024

6.2.1 Audience insights

Audience insights: Measure your performance by analyzing your X (Twitter) Page activity

Audience growth

Number of net followers gained during the selected period.

New followers (net)	257
Total followers	1834

The total audience is

1834

representing a variation of **+21.2%**
 compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Engagement

Number of followers' interactions (likes, replies and reposts) with your profile for the selected period.

Mentions	405
Likes	2K
Replies	19
Quote posts	169
Reposts	807
Direct messages	18
Total interactions	3.4K

The total engagement is
3,414 interactions
 representing a variation of **+133.4%**
 compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Hashtags & interactions

Number of interactions generated by hashtags used in your posts.

#missionocean 2541 Interactions	#horizoneu 865 Interactions	#eumissions 814 Interactions	#generationblue 626 Interactions
#ecops 504 Interactions	#oceandecade 491 Interactions	#vecops24 380 Interactions	#marine 310 Interactions
#euoceandays 251 Interactions	#mediterranean 217 Interactions	#vecop24 173 Interactions	#ecopdays24 151 Interactions
#oceandecade24 144 Interactions	#mission 142 Interactions	#ecosystems 110 Interactions	#pollution 100 Interactions
#roadmap 96 Interactions	#opencall 89 Interactions	#atlantic 79 Interactions	#lighthouseinnovation 77 Interactions

Overview

Key performance metrics for the selected period.

Users' activity

Average day and hour users interacted the most with the profile's content. Based on inbox activities (mentions and direct messages).

6.2.2 Content summary

Content summary: Evaluate the lifetime performance of published content on your X (Twitter) Page

Best day and time to publish

Average day and hour followers are most likely to engage with published content.

Best post type to publish

Type of post followers are most likely to engage with.

Overview

Lifetime metrics of content published during the selected period.

Publishing

Number of Posts published during the selected period -with breakdown by type.

Text	13
Links	27
Photos/Videos	287
Total posts published	327

The total number of posts published is
327
representing a variation of **+127.1%**
compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on impressions.

Mar. 22 2024	Mar. 28 2024	Mar. 5 2024
Dive into change!	How can we protect and restore islands' marine ...	Today the 2nd Annual Forum of the Mission 'Restore...
Impressions	Impressions	Impressions
4.4K	2.4K	2.4K
Likes	Likes	Likes
39	15	42
Reposts	Reposts	Reposts
28	7	12
Quote posts	Quote posts	Quote posts
5	1	5
Replies	Replies	Replies
1	1	1
Engagement	Engagement	Engagement
181	44	125
Engagement rate per impression	Engagement rate per impression	Engagement rate per impression
4.1%	1.8%	5.3%

Top content

Best performing content published during the selected period. Based on impressions.

May. 3 2024	Apr. 12 2024	May. 17 2024
Ports are stewards of #sustainability.	Key takeaways from our opening speakers at The #Me...	The deadline to apply for technical assistance is ...
Impressions	Impressions	Impressions
2.1K	1.8K	1.8K
Likes	Likes	Likes
11	11	15
Reposts	Reposts	Reposts
6	3	8
Quote posts	Quote posts	Quote posts
0	1	1
Replies	Replies	Replies
1	0	2
Engagement	Engagement	Engagement
33	38	58
Engagement rate per impression	Engagement rate per impression	Engagement rate per impression
1.6%	2.1%	3.6%

6.2.3 Community management

Community management: Understand the amount of work invested in your team's community management actions.

Overview

Key metrics of community management actions during the selected period.

Replies sent

Number of replies to comments sent during the selected period.

The total number of replies is
16
 representing a variation of **+166.7%**
 compared to Oct. 8 2023 –Jan. 31 2024

7 Youtube

In the selected period, your channel got 16 views

Channel analytics

ADVANCED MODE

Overview Content Audience Inspiration

Feb 1 - May 26, 2024
Custom

In the selected period, your channel got 16 views

Realtime

Updating live

19

Subscribers

SEE LIVE COUNT

112

Views - Last 48 hours

Top content

Views

	Witness the industrious spir...	58
	Part 1: Arctic Ocean warmin...	16
	Part 2: Ocean observing vide...	14

Channel analytics

Overview Content Audience Inspiration

In the selected period, your channel got 16 views

Channel
MissionOceanWaters

Content	Publish date	Last 48 hours	Last 60 minutes
Witness the industrious spirit of a beaver	May 29, 2024	58	0
Part 1: Arctic Ocean warming - video compilation from MoJ...	May 29, 2024	16	0
Part 2: Ocean observing video compilation from MoJo Fiona	May 29, 2024	14	0
Part 2: Arctic Ocean warming - video compilation from MoJ...	May 29, 2024	9	0
A warming Arctic Ocean	May 29, 2024	6	0
A closer look at the melting glacier in the Arctic Ocean	May 29, 2024	4	0
Part 2: Explore the complexities of nature's delicate balance...	May 29, 2024	2	0
Introducing Resilient Oceans project	May 29, 2024	1	0
Part 1: Explore the complexities of nature's delicate balance...	May 29, 2024	1	0
The role of young people in climate activism	May 29, 2024	1	0

Top playlists

Playlist	Views from playlist ↓	Total views
1 EU Missions Updated 1 year ago	1	0
2 Interviews UN Ocean Conference (27.June-01.July2022) Updated 1 year ago	0	16

SEE MORE